

CONTEMPORARY STYLISTICS AND THE ISSUES OF ADVERTISING SLOGAN

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Annotation. This article is devoted to the problems of advertisement and advertising slogan which discusses special features of slogans and studies slogans stylistic point of view.

Key words: slogan, stylistics, literary criticism, generative grammar, literary texts.

Stylistics in the twentieth century replaced and expanded on the earlier study of Rhetoric. Following the publication of a two-volume research on French stylistics by Bally (1909), Saussure, interest in stylistics gradually spread across Europe via the work of Spitzer (1928,1948) and others. It was in the 1960s that it really began to flourish in Britain and the United States . In many respects, however, stylistics is close to literary criticism and Practical Criticism. By far the most common kind of material studied is literary; and attention is largely TEXT-centred. The goal of most stylistic studies is not simply to describe the formal features of texts for their own sake, but in order to show their functional significance for the interpretation of the text; or in order to relate literary effects or themes to linguistic "triggers" where these are felt to be relevant. Intuitions and interpretative skills are just as important in stylistics and literary criticism; however, stylisticians want to avoid vague and impressionistic judgments about the way formal features are manipulated.

As a result, stylistics continually reassumes its models and terminology in the light of new developments in linguistics. In the late 1960s generative grammar was influential; in the 1970s and 1980s Discourse analysis and pragmatics; in the 1990s critical discourse analysis and cognitive linguistics. Stylistics also draws on trends in literary theory. So, the 1970s saw a shift away from the text itself to the reader and is now broadly concerned with how we understand a text and are affected by it. Stylistics is sometimes called literary stylistics and linguistic stylistics: literary because it tends to focus on literary texts; linguistic because its models or tools are drawn from linguistics. However, linguistic stylistics has also referred to a kind of stylistics whose focus of interest is not

primarily literary texts, but the 32 refinement of a linguistic model which has potential for further linguistic or stylistic analysis. Stylistics is the study and analysis of texts; it is in particular, although not exclusively, the study and analysis of literary texts. The origins of stylistics go back to the poetics, and especially to the rhetoric, of the ancient classical world. In ancient rhetoric it is principally the third of the five canons which is of importance to stylistics . Stylistics is interdisciplinary in scope – most obviously so by its bringing together linguistics and literary studies. The field have furthermore allowed views borrowed from disciplines such as philosophy, cultural theory, sociology, history and psychology to find their way into the stylistic analyses of literature. While sometimes criticized for its interdisciplinary, stylistics has been praised by others for its interdisciplinary character which is considered one of the advantages and inspiring potentials of the approach . Stylistics is often regarded as a linguistic approach to literature – and understandably so, since the majority of stylistic attention so far has been devoted to literary texts. In actual fact, however, the range of discourses that stylisticians are currently engaged with has expanded considerably to include non-fictional forms such as advertising, academic writing, news reports as well as non-printed forms such as TV and pictorial advertising, film, multimodal publications, etc. With its base in linguistics, stylistics is characterized by an informed, systematic, retrievable, and contextual analysis, which is rigorous, consistent and open to falsification. Because of the ‘scientific’ nature of linguistics as compared to other fields in the humanities, the stylistic approach to text analysis may seem more objective than other branches of literary criticism. It is important to note, however, that in spite of stylisticians’ concern with rigour, no stylistic analysis can be totally objective, but it will always be influenced by a myriad of factors, such as the stylistician’s individual preferences and foci, as well as the linguistic paradigm 33 employed for analysis or the chosen methodology.

Stylistics is the study of the ways in which meaning is created through language in literature as well as in other types of text. To this end, stylisticians use linguistic models, theories and frameworks as their analytical tools in order to describe and explain how and why a text works as it does, and how we come from the words on the page to its meaning. The analysis typically focuses qualitatively or quantitatively on the phonological, lexical, grammatical, semantic, pragmatic or discoursal features of texts, on the cognitive aspects involved in the processing of those features by the reader as well as on various combinations of these. While some stylistic approaches primarily show an

interest in the producer of the text, investigating the style of a particular author, for instance, other stylisticians focus more on the text itself and still others devote their attention to the reader and the role readers play in meaning construction. New developments in stylistics emphasize that the production of meaning needs to be accounted for as a double exercise encompassing as much text-informed inferences as the mental processes that allow text comprehension. Stylistics or general stylistics can be used as a cover term to cover the analyses of non-literary varieties of language, or registers. Because of this broad scope, stylistics comes close to work done in sociolinguistics. Indeed, sociostylistics studies, for instance, the language of writers considered as social groups (e.g. the Elizabethan university wits; pamphleteers); or 'fashions' in language. [Wales 1990:191]. Stylistics is a linguistic discipline which studies nominative and communicative language units and the principles according to which the units of all language levels are selected for achieving a certain pragmatic aim in different communicative situations. Stylistics, as a field of study devoted to understanding the relationship between textual features and readerly effects, is in some sense necessarily pragmatic. Nevertheless, pragmatic theories can help stylisticians to move towards a more rigorous engagement with context by linking the readers' experiences and evaluations of style to the conventions, norms and values of the societies in which texts are produced and received.

Contemporary stylistics goes far beyond the rhetoric, poetics, formalism, structuralism, gender, multimodal and, most recently, neuroscientific approaches. This diversity might have the initial appearance of fragmenting the field. However, nothing could be further from the truth, because at many levels, interdisciplinarity study is what stylistics is designed to do. As stylistician Paul Simpson writes, 'stylistics is a method of textual interpretation in which primacy of place is assigned to language'. Stylistics in the early twenty-first century is very much alive and well. It is taught and researched in university departments of language, literature and linguistics the world over. The high academic profile stylistics enjoys is mirrored in the number of its dedicated book-length publications, research journals, international conferences and symposia, and scholarly associations. Far from moribund, modern stylistics is positively flourishing, witnessed in a proliferation of sub-disciplines where stylistic methods are enriched and enabled by theories of discourse, culture and society.

Stylistics thus still carries the methodological genes that it has inherited from its forebear, rhetoric. Its very purpose is its application to textual data, and its strength lies in its potential for such application. Stylistics is a method of textual

interpretation in which primacy of place is assigned to language. The reason why language is so important to stylisticians is because the various forms, patterns and levels that constitute linguistic structure are an important index of the function of the text. The text's functional significance as discourse acts in turn as a gateway to its interpretation. While linguistic features do not of themselves constitute a text's 'meaning', an account of linguistic features nonetheless serves to ground a stylistic interpretation and to help explain why, for the analyst, certain types of meaning are 35 possible. The traditional connection between stylistics and literature brings with it two important caveats, though to do stylistics is to explore language, and, more specifically, to explore creativity in language use. Doing stylistics thereby enriches our ways of thinking about language and, as observed, exploring language offers a substantial purchase on our understanding of (literary) texts. Interest in language is always at the fore in contemporary stylistic analysis which is why you should never undertake to do stylistics unless you are interested in language. As Geoffrey Leech and Mick Short, stylistics, simply defined as the (linguistic) study of style, is rarely undertaken for its own sake, simply as an exercise in describing what use is made of language. We normally study style because we want to explain something, and in general, literary stylistics has, implicitly or explicitly, the goal of explaining the relation between language and artistic function.

A figure of speech is popularly associated with such expressive devices of language as metaphor and simile, by which images are evoked through comparison of one 'object' with another: e.g. Women are angels, wooing; Time is like a fashionable host (Shakespeare: Troilus and Cressida). In rhetoric, whence the origin of the term, figures of speech are actually much more numerous than those given in, and far more diverse in their nature, so that it is difficult to define their essential feature. Plett (1977) defines the figure as 'the smallest DEVIANT language unit', which implies controversially that figures generally depart from the linguistic 'norms' of everyday language in some way, whether semantically, or syntactically. This is possibly the case if we see deviations as not only rule-breaking, but also over-regular. Originating in classical oratory as devices to structure and elaborate an argument, 36 and to move the emotions of an audience, figures of speech soon came to be associated with the art of literary composition. According I.R. Galperin, stylistic device is "a conscious and intentional intensification of some typical structural and/or semantic property of a language unit (neutral or expressive) promoted to a generalized status and

thus becoming a generative model". It follows then that an SD is an abstract pattern, a mould into which any content can be poured. As is known, the typical is not only that which is in frequent use, but that also which reveals the essence of a phenomenon with the greatest and most evident force. Broadly, figures are traditionally divided into SCHEMES and TROPES, of which schemes are by far the most frequent.

A linguistic reinterpretation of the traditional distinction between schemes and tropes is given in Leech (1969), schemes are defined as 'foregrounded repetitions of expression', and tropes as 'foregrounded irregularities of content'. Various kinds of scheme, corresponding to traditional figures of speech such as 'anaphora' and 'antithesis' are discussed in Leech (1969), The line between these two categories, as with many other rhetorical classifications, has always been vaguely and inconsistently drawn. Schemes, roughly, have included figures such as alliteration, anaphora, and chiasmus, and have been described as abnormal arrangements lending themselves to the forceful and harmonious presentation of ideas. Tropes, more radical in scope and more powerful in effect, have (again roughly) been identified as devices involving alteration of the normal meaning of an expression: they include metaphor, irony, and synecdoche. Some rhetoricians draw up a third category of 'figures of thought'. These are more concerned with the psychological strategy of developing a theme than with the actual choice of language, and so lie outside our province. Leech sees no harm in resurrecting the division between the schemes and tropes, and reinterpreting it on a more strictly linguistic basis. Schemes have to do with expression, and tropes with content: this much is traditional. Schemes and tropes are identified at different levels: i.e. a scheme may be identified as a phonological, a graphological, or a formal (i.e. grammatical and/or lexical) pattern; likewise, a trope may be identified as a formal or a semantic deviation. But these identifications are not so distinct as they may seem, because there is a great deal of interdependence between the levels. [Leech, 1969:74-75] In the last two decades or so, that is from the 1980s and onwards, both linguistic semantics and other, related disciplines that deal with meaning and thinking have seen a steadily increasing interest in figurative language. More specifically, this interest has centred on the occurrence of words and formulations that have some kind of extended or transferred meaning. Tropes is a cover term from traditional rhetoric for language uses with some kind of secondary meaning. In other words, the meaning of a trope has come about through some obvious shift from a more basic type of understanding of a language element. Literary interest

in, and use of, figures of speech reached its zenith in the Renaissance: Peacham's (1577) handbook lists nearly 200 different types. Poets handled them with verve and ostentation, having learned their names as part of their grammar school education and their study of ELOCUTIO. A decline in the study of classics, and a growing suspicion of the rhetorical, have led to a decline in their use in literary composition and public speaking, although a 'hard core' of figures still persists, and some are known reasonably well by name. Devices of repetition are common in public speaking; and FIGURATIVE LANGUAGE is generally characteristic of advertising, for example. Indeed, new figures unknown in traditional rhetoric have to be accounted for here: e.g. GRAPHEMIC deviations in brand names. Undoubtedly, a knowledge of stylistic figures is of considerable importance for our understanding of stylistic effect in literary language in earlier periods. 38 In the second half of the twentieth century, however, renewed interest in figures of speech came from French structuralism influenced by the earlier Russian formalists; from deconstruction theory; from stylistics in work on text analysis; speech act theory; cognitive linguistics and pragmatics. As a result, there have been several attempts at new classifications of figures.

The occurrence of novel figures of speech is one effect of the creativity of a language, although there is of course also a host of established figurative uses. More specifically, the construction of novel figures of speech shows that the need to express thoughts and impressions that have no conventional verbal representations can make us invest words with new meanings. However, if a novel figure of speech is repeatedly used by the members of a speech community after it has been introduced in their language, it becomes a conventional part of it. So, both conventionalised and merely incidental polysemous shifts reflect the flexibility of verbal languages in dealing with the infinitely complex nature of human experiences, thoughts and reactions. A rhetorical figure can be defined as an artful deviation in the form taken by a statement. Since antiquity dozens of figures have been cataloged, ranging from the familiar (rhyme, pun) to the obscure (antimetabole). Despite the frequent appearance of rhetorical figures in print advertisements, their incorporation into advertising theory and research has been minimal. In fact, from the perspective of advertising theory, previous efforts to systematize the set of rhetorical figures have all been handicapped by one or more of the following shortcomings: the taxonomic categories are vague or too coarse grained, the categories are not linked to consumer responses, or the focus is on outcomes other than persuasion.

References:

1. Williamson, J.W. (1978) //Decoding advertisements. Ideology and meaning in advertising. London: Marion Boyars. Dictionary 2001.
2. Ungerer, F. 'Muted Metaphors and the Activation of Metonymies in Advertising'. [In] Barcelona, A. (ed.), 2000. 321-340.
3. Norgaard N., Montoro R., Busse B. Key terms in Stylistics New York. 2010.
4. Leech, G. H., English in Advertising. A Linguistic Study of Advertising in Great Britain. London: Longman, XIV. 1966;
5. Crystal D., Davy, D. Investigating English Style. Harlow: Addison Wesley Longman, 1969. 264 p
6. Dean D. Brand endorsement, popularity, and event sponsorship as advertising cues affecting consumer pre-purchase attitudes. Journal of Advertising, 1-12. 1999.
7. Пазилова Н, Турдубекова И "The investigation of syntactical expressive means and stylistic devices in Modern English and Uzbek" International Journal of Research in commerce, IT, Engineering and Social Sciences ISSN No: 2349-7793 VOLUME16, Issue 01 January, 2022
8. Pazilova Nasibaxon, Yuldashev L "Effective ways of teaching and expanding vocabulary" ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions vISSN: 2776-0960 Impact Factor: 7.655 VOLUME 2, ISSUE 5, MAY-2021 Website: <http://reserchjet.academiascience.org>
9. Diez Arroyo M. La retorica del mensaje publicitario. Un estudio de la publicidad inglesa. Universidad de Oviedo: Servicio de Publicaciones. 1998.

